

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for tryptophan metabolite analysis of urine via LC-QQQ

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Summary

The tryptophan metabolites (anthranilate, indole-3-acetamide, indole-3-acetate, indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid, L-kynurenine, L-tryptophan, methyl indole-3-acetate, methyl indole-3-propionic acid, N-acetyl tryptophan, tryptamine) perform important signalling and immunomodulatory functions, especially interaction of the innate immune system of the host with PXR or AHR xenobiotic receptors. This protocol describe preparation of urine and quantitative/semiquantitative determination using LC-QQQ. Compare with another human matrices, urine can be easily collected non-invasively, however intra-and inter-individual urine volume and thus concentration of metabolites varies (>15-fold) during daytime; in relation with dietary, hormonal, psychological and behavioural factors. Therefore, normalization of samples is necessary; typically as the ration of metabolite concentration to creatinine concentration. However, the recommended type of normalization is pre-acquisition normalization i.e. before analysis; using specific gravity measurement; see **SOP for pre-acquisition normalisation of urine via specific gravity**.

Due to the different amounts of metabolites in the urine (within several orders of magnitude) it is necessary to prepare and measure samples with multiple dilutions.

Preparation

Safety information

- Urine samples are classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- Isopropanol: flammable liquids, eye irritation, specific target organ toxicity following single exposure

Equipment

- 100 µL multichannel, 250 µL multichannel pipettes & 1 mL pipettes
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates

Consumables & glassware

- 4 mL screw cap glass vial and cap
- 1000 µL 96-well plates with silicone sealing
- 250 µL & 1 mL tips

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

- Urine samples stored in -80°C freezer and thawed at room temperature

Labelled standard mix:

[¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful, irritating

[²H₅] L-kynurenine (99 % isotope enrichment)

[¹³C₁₁][¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan (99 % isotope enrichment)

[²H₅] [¹⁵N] indole-3-acetamide (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful

[¹³C₆] anthranilate (99 % isotope enrichment) – harmful

[²H₃] creatinine (99 % isotope enrichment) - irritating

Indolmix (native standard mix) each = 250 nM in 25 % (v/v) isopropanol

methyl indole-3-acetate – corrosive, irritant

methyl indole-3-propionic acid - irritant

tryptamine - irritant

indol-3-acetic acid – harmful, irritating

L-kynurenine

L-tryptophan

indol-3-acetamide - harmful

anthranilate - harmful

N-acetyl-tryptophan – harmful, irritating

indol-3-aldehyde - irritating

indol-3-lactic acid – irritating

creatinine - irritating

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- Acetonitrile, LC-MS grade
- Formic acid (FA), LC-MS grade
- MilliQ water

Procedure

Standard preparation

1. Prepare 3 mL aliquots of 1000 nM [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] indole-3-acetate acid, 1000 nM indole-3-acetamide [$^2\text{H}_5$] [^{15}N] and 500 nM anthranilate [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] in 5 % (v/v) isopropanol
2. Pipette directly or dry the internal reference standard mix down in Centrifugal evaporator at laboratory temperature, store in -80°C and reconstitute in the solvent before analysis.

Sample preparation

1. NOTE: Store urine samples at -80°C
2. Take out urine samples from freezer and leave at room temperature to thaw
3. Pipette 250 μL of urine sample and dry in Centrifugal evaporator
4. To the dried sample add 200 μL of 80% (v/v) isopropanol; sonicate (30 s); vortex (200 RPM at room temperature) for 10 min; centrifuge for 10 min at 4000 RPM (use centrifuge for 96-well plates)
5. Afterwards remove 150 μL of the supernatant
6. To the remaining 50 μL of the sample add 200 μL of 80% (v/v) isopropanol; sonicate (30 s); vortex (200 RPM at room temperature) for 10 min; centrifuge for 10 min at 4000 RPM (use centrifuge for 96-well plates)
7. Afterwards remove 200 μL of the supernatant
8. The extract from two extraction step mix together to create stock extract
9. Pipette 40 μL of the stock extract and dry in Centrifugal evaporator
10. Redissolve the stock extract in 20 μL 5% (v/v) isopropanol standard mix containing: [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] indole-3-acetate, [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] anthranilic acid, [$^2\text{H}_5$] [^{15}N] indole-3-acetamide in 5% (v/v) isopropanol, leading to a concentration in samples of 1000 nM, 500 nM and 1000 nM, respectively.
11. Dilute stock extract 500 times for tryptophan and kynurenine determination and spike with [$^2\text{D}_4$] L-kynurenine and [$^{13}\text{C}_{11}$] [$^{15}\text{N}_2$] L-tryptophan leading to concentration in sample 200 nM and 3000 nM, respectively

NOTE: dilute the sample due to relatively high concentration kynurenine and tryptophan in urine

Dilute the stock extract 60 000 times for creatinine determination, spike with [²H₃] creatinine leading to the concentration in sample 60 nM

NOTE: dilute the sample due to high concentration creatinine in urine

Mobile phase preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water (solution can be kept for 7 days at 4°C temperature)
- Mobile phase B: 0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile

NOTE: use at least 5% milliQ water in acetonitrile (prevent LC clogging)

LC-QQQ analysis

3. Clean the source and nebulizer before measurement
4. Check solvent for needle rinsing
5. Check solvent for seals rinsing
6. Prepare mobile phase
7. Input sequence
8. Start LC-QQQ analysis run
9. Check initial blanks, standard mix = Indolmix, Labelled standard mix and QC

NOTE: If problems, stop run, cap samples and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.

NOTE: Measure with every sample set:

- Instrument blank (Mobile phase A)
- Procedural blank (same preparation as samples; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC (pool of samples extract; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC dilution series in 3 replicates (same sample preparation as QC with 2x, 4x, 8x dilution & spiked with Labelled standard mix)
- Indolmix
- Labelled standard mix in 5% (v/v) isopropanol
- Calibration curve in matrix: prepare pool of DBS extract → spike Labelled standard mix (use 6 different concentration) → measure 6 calibration points with 3 replicates (6 replicates for LOD, LOQ determination)
- QC_dilution series in 3 replicates (dilute QC: 2x, 4x, 8x & spike with same concentration of Labelled standard mix)

LC-QQQ sequence setup

1. Clean_blank
2. Clean_blank
3. Instrument blank
4. Indolmix
5. Indolmix
6. Indolmix
7. Labelled standard mix
8. QC_dilution series
9. Procedural blank
10. QC sample
11. Samples 1-3
12. Instrument blank
13. Sample 4-6
14. Instrument blank
15. Sample 7-9 ...

NOTE: measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples

NOTE: measure Indolmix with every 30 samples

NOTE: measure Labelled standard mix minimum 3 times (at the beginning of the batch, in the middle of the batch and the end of the batch)

16. Calibration
17. End with Indolmix, Instrument blank and 2 x Clean blank

Table 1. SRM assay library for positive ion detection mode

COMPOUND	PRECURSOR	PRODUCT	RT [MIN]
[² H ₃] CREATININE	117.09	47.2	0.9
[² H ₃] CREATININE	117.09	43.2	0.9
CREATININE	114.00	44.1	0.9
CREATININE	114.00	86	0.9
L-KYNURENINE*	209.09	192.00	1.6
L-KYNURENINE	209.09	94.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE*	215.13	198.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE	215.13	96.10	1.6
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	144.1	1.9
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	117	1.9
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	115	1.9
TRYPTAMINE	161.11	91	1.9
L-TRYPTOPHAN *	205.10	188.00	2.9
L-TRYPTOPHAN	205.10	91.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN*	218.10	200.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN	218.10	98.10	2.9
ANTHRANILIC ACID	138.06	120.00	7.2
ANTHRANILIC ACID*	138.06	65.00	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID	144.08	126.10	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID*	144.08	70.20	7.2
INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE*	175.09	130.07	7.3
INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE	175.09	103.00	7.3
[² H ₅] [¹⁵ N] INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE*	181.12	134.10	7.3
[² H ₅] [¹⁵ N] INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE	181.12	106.00	7.3
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN*	247.11	188.10	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN	247.11	130.00	7.8

N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN	247.11	118.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	188.00	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	130.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTID ACID*	206.06	117.90	7.8
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE*	146.06	118.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	117.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	91.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	65.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	39.20	8.0
INDOLE-3-ACETATE*	176.07	130.07	8.2
[¹³ C ₆] INDOLE-3-ACETATE*	182.10	136.10	8.2
METLYLINDOL-3-ACETATE	190.09	130.07	9.3
METHYL INDOLE-3-PROPIONATE	204.1	130.07	9.7
METHYL INDOLE-3-PROPIONATE	204.1	77	9.7

* Transition used for quantification

SRM metabolite quantitative/semi-quantitative evaluation

1. For concentration determination of indole-3-acetic acid, L-kynurenine, L-tryptophan, anthranilate, indol-3-acetamide and creatinine use internal standardization with isotopically labelled standards [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate, [²D₄] L-kynurenine, [¹³C₁₁] [¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan, [¹³C₆] anthranilate, indole-3-acetamide [²H₅] [¹⁵N] and [²H₃] creatinine.

The calculation is based on the concentration of isotopically labelled standard added to DBS sample, measured response (integrated peak area) of isotopically labelled standard, and response (integrated peak area) of metabolite Equation (1).

$$c_{\text{met}} = \left(\frac{C_{\text{IS}}}{A_{\text{IS}}} \times A_{\text{met}} \right) \quad (1)$$

2. For the lack of commercially available standards, the concentration of indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid, methyl indole-3-acetate, methyl indole-3-propionic acid, N-acetyl tryptophan, tryptamine are determined with response factor (RF) Equation (2).

NOTE: use [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate as a C_{IS}

$$c_{\text{met}} = \left(\frac{C_{\text{IS}}}{A_{\text{IS}}} \times A_{\text{met}} \right) : \text{RF} \quad (2)$$

RF are calculated from Indolmix and Labelled standard mix determined in Equation (3)

$$\text{RF} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{met}}}{A_{\text{IS}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{IS}}}{C_{\text{met}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

NOTE: no normalization used

LC-QQQ method setup

Multisampler settings

Injection volume			2 µL
Needle Wash			Multi-wash
Stoptime			As Pump/No Limit
Posttime			Off
Advanced	Sampling Speed	Draw Speed	100 µL/min
		Eject Speed	100 µL/min
		Wait time After Draw	0 s
	Needle Height position	Offset	-0.4 mm
		Use Vial/Well Bottom Sensing	Yes
	High Throughput	Sample Flush-Out factor	5.0
		Injection Valve to Bypass for Delay Volume Reduction	No
		Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Binary Pump

Flow	0.3 mL/min		
Solvents	A:	0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water	
	B:	0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile	
Pressure limits	Min	0 bar	
	Max	1200 bar	
Stoptime	14 min		
Posttime	Off		
Advanced: Timetable	Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]
	0	95	5
	5	90	10
	10	5	95
	11.99	5	95
	12.00	95	5
	14.00	95	5

Column comp

Temperature	40 °C		
Advanced	Enable analysis	When temperature is within	± 0.8 °C

QQQ

Source parameters	Gas Temp:	160 °C
	Gas Flow:	15 L/min
	Nebulizer:	25 psi
	Sheath Gas Temp:	250 °C
	Sheath Gas Flow:	12 L/min

iFunnel parameters	Capillary:	3500 V (Positive)	3000 V (Negative)
	Nozzle Voltage:	500 V (Positive)	1500 V (Negative)
	High Pressure RF	150 V (Positive)	90 V (Negative)
	Low Pressure RF	60 V (Positive)	60 V (Negative)
Chromatogram	Stop Time		
	No limit/As Pump		
Time segments	Ion source	AJS ESI	
	Time filtering	Peak width	0.05 min
	Start Time	Scan type	Div Valve
	1	0	MRM
2	10.5	MRM	To Waste

Column & guard column: Acquity UHPLC CSHTM C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm) & VanGuard ACQUITY UPLC CSH C18 (5 x 2.1 mm; 1.7 µm) from Waters